

FACTSHEET #4

Narrative based simulation game and interactive explainers

The narrative based simulation game and the interactive explainers regard the co-creation with citizens of both educational materials and a game. The topic of these materials and games revolve around critical digital literacy.

Participants in the use cases define the specific topic of the materials as well as the format of the games and materials themselves. In these activities, the presence of the Trinity College Dublin ensures the execution of a coherent testing methodology with the rest of the research activities. The Institute of Urban and Regional Development (IRMiR) executes the methodologies in Poland and collaborate in the design of the testing methodology drawing mostly with their great expertise in citizen science. Hybrid Core is responsible for the technical development of the game and materials, HYC is also engaged in testing methodology to ensure realism and offer valuable insights. Fundación Cibervoluntarios (CIB) is the mastermind behind testing methodology design. CIB executes it in Spain, taking charge of coordinating the entire research and testing initiative. Their extensive experience in user-centric approaches and testing methodology from similar projects is invaluable.

Who is involved in the development process

CIBER
VOLUNTARIOS.org

HYBRID CORE

Trinity College Dublin
Coláiste na Tríonóide, Baile Átha Cliath
The University of Dublin

IRMiR INSTITUTE OF
URBAN AND REGIONAL
DEVELOPMENT

Stakeholders

The external stakeholders are citizens from Poland and Spain carefully selected from a sample in which age diversity, LGBT, vulnerable collectives and attitude towards participation are key indicators.

Testing

During the first iteration, a total of 60 participants are involved in the co-creation methodologies. There will be two main iterations as stated below. The first one takes place in 2023 and consists on a co-creation workshop in which participants imagine materials and games. The second takes place once the materials and games are ready. It consists of a testing and validation of such outputs for further refinements.

CHALLENGES / Why is it important?

The narrative based simulation game and the interactive explainers are a tangible output of the project. They directly aim at raising awareness towards participation and democracy. The interaction with this game and materials will surely be a valuable asset for educators, learners and in general the public to learn in an engaging way and exercise their critical thinking.

Nonetheless, this narrative based simulation game and the interactive explainers brings its challenges. Time is necessary in the development of a game, and its constraints must be taken into account. At the same time, the game and materials should be engaging enough for users to find them really useful. Finally, the conveyance of the research work, with the game development and user's feedback is challenging as well. Nonetheless all these challenges are being addressed. The schedule of development is already clear, the user's involvement will be crucial to ensure the game is engaging and the channels of communication are established and fluent for a harmonic transmission of everyone's needs and capacities.

Benefits and beneficiaries

The beneficiaries of this KER are citizens in general and more particularly educators and learners, always taking the notion of learners in a wide sense. They will benefit from engaging materials and games that will exercise their critical thinking. This reverts to a more informed, less polarised and more immune to disinformation society.

"We believe in the importance of building participatory processes that strengthen the social fabric. By fostering co-creation, we aim to expand digital literacies and generate a positive impact across diverse communities."

César García Martínez (Fundación Cibervoluntarios) Social and Cultural Anthropologist and Master in Intercultural Education

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